

COVID-19 DURING PREGNANCY

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Objective: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is the cause of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) disease that has rapidly spread worldwide, causing hundreds of thousand deaths. Normal placentation is characterized by many processes strictly regulated during pregnancy. The SARS-CoV-2 infection causes COVID-19 disease, characterized by acute respiratory distress syndrome, bilateral pneumonia, and organ failure. The consequences of maternal SARS-CoV-2 infection for the pregnant woman, fetus, and neonate are controversial. Thus, it is required to determine whether there is viral and non-viral vertical transmission in COVID-19. The disease caused by SARS-CoV-2 leads to functional alterations in asymptomatic and symptomatic pregnant women, the fetoplacental unit and the neonate. Several diseases of pregnancy, including COVID-19, affect the fetoplacental function, which causes in utero programming for young and adult diseases. A generalized inflammatory state and a higher risk of infection are seen in pregnant women with COVID-19. Obesity, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension may increase the vulnerability of pregnant women to infection by SARS-CoV-2. Alpha, Delta, and Omicron variants of SARS-CoV-2 show specific mutations that seem to increase the capacity of the virus to infect the pregnant woman, likely due to increasing its interaction via the virus S protein and angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 receptors. This review shows the literature addressing to what extent COVID-19 in pregnancy affects the pregnant woman, fetoplacental unit, and neonate.

Keywords: Covid-19; Pregnancy; Sars-Cov-2.

Methods: We collected 28 pregnant women who were infected with SARS-CoV-2 and accepted treatment 3rd birth center in Tashkent from March 2020 till August 2022

for our researcher work. Collected information included general medical and obstetrics history as well as the pregnancy outcome of the index pregnancy. Patients' charts were used to obtain this information. Obstetrics information were obtained as described elsewhere. Small for gestational age (SGA) and large for gestational age (LGA) were defined as a newborn weight 90 centile, respectively. Centiles were determined using the local referral values. The questionnaire that women had to fill evaluated the presence of symptoms suggestive for Covid-19 over the last three months. More than one episode of symptoms could be reported. The specific items included in the questionnaire are illustrated in details elsewhere. Briefly, they include the presence of fever (≥ 37.5 °C), cough, sore throat, rhinitis, headache, diarrhea, vomit, dyspnea (including tachypnea), asthenia, myalgia, anosmia and ageusia. In addition, women were asked if they were exposed to higher risk of infection for job situations (health workers or laboratory technicians) or contacts with persons with a definitive diagnosis of Covid-19 or cohabitant with persons doing a job at risk or having symptoms suggestive for Covid-19. Evaluation of Covid-19 in the cohort was based on three determinations: identification of the specific RNA on a nasopharyngeal swab and research of Immunoglobuline (Ig) using two different tests.

Results: Overall, 28 women had a diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2 infection in pregnancy (8.9%). Women diagnosed with the infection were more likely to report one or more episodes of symptoms suggestive for Covid-19 ($n = 11$, 39.3%) compared to unaffected women ($n = 39$, 13.6%). Symptoms significantly associated with Covid-19 in pregnancy included fever, cough, dyspnea and anosmia. Only one woman necessitated intensive care. Pregnancy outcome in women with and without SARS-CoV-2 infection did not also differ. Three hundred eighty-five women delivered during the study period. Twelve were excluded because they were referred from other hospitals for Covid-19. Thirty-five were not recruited because of violation of the study protocol (the study was not proposed). Twenty-three women refused to participate. Three hundred fifteen women were ultimately enrolled. Overall, 28 women had a diagnosis of Sars-Cov-2 infection (8.9%, 95%CI: 6.2–12.5%), of whom 13 were

identified with (RT)- PCR. The median (range) number of RT-PCR cycles needed to highlight positivity was 35.2 (13.5–39.7). To note, among the 24 women who were detected with antibodies against Sars-Cov-2, 17 (71%) were positive to both tests used, three (12%) were positive only for antibodies against the envelope and four (17%) only to those against the nucleoprotein. No maternal deaths occurred. No SARS-Cov-2 neonatal infections at birth were observed.

Conclusions: SARS-CoV-2 infection is asymptomatic in three out of five women in late pregnancy and is rarely severe. In addition, pregnancy outcome may not be markedly affected.

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